

From Accessibility to Inclusion in Public Toilets: A Technology Perspective

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Abstract

As of 2021, more than 7 million toilets have been constructed in the Indian cities and owing to the well-meaning attempts of the Indian government this number is increasing. Inclusion, however, continues to remain a challenge as the need for accessibility in public toilets remains unattended. While access to public sanitation has wide ranging interpretations of availability, usability, and affordability, it is vital to consider diverse technologies as a catalyst towards creating more inclusive environments in public toilets. Numerous innovations and developments are taking place in this domain both locally and globally. This paper intends to bring an insight into the industry of various technologies that could enhance accessibility as an experience in public toilets. It presents a review of such technologies from distinct national and international case studies of accessibility in public toilet

experiences. It assesses each case along various dimensions, including the principles of universal design like equitable use, flexibility, tolerance for error, etc. The outcome informs the way forward for technological innovations in public toilets and presents the key best practices, as derived from the case studies. It further highlights the challenges and possible limitations in the use of technology for accessibility and inclusion in public toilets.

Keywords: *accessibility, inclusion, public toilets, sanitation, technology, universal design, innovation*

Introduction

Public Toilets form an essential part of the overall WASH (Water, Sanitation and Hygiene) ecosystem of any city or urban area. Equitable access to the same is a fundamental need of all, and this is emphasised in Goal 6 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Numerous countries, including India, have worked towards this goal through programs and schemes namely, the Swachh Bharat (Clean India) Mission. Under this initiative, more than 7 million toilets have been constructed in the Indian cities (Press Trust of India, 2021).

Zallio and Clarkson (2021) define inclusion in its expanded form, that is, it includes understanding how people behave, socialise, live, and access the place. It goes beyond simply creating designs or technologies that are functional for persons with disabilities. If inclusion is understood to be the end goal, then accessibility may be understood as an attribute or trait of any product, space, or technology, which nudges it towards the end goal. Accessibility and inclusion in the context of public toilets have various wide-ranging interpretations like availability, usability, affordability, safety, hygiene, etc.

Technology can play a crucial role to create more inclusive

public toilet environments across all the above-mentioned dimensions and in accordance with the various principles of universal design. The intent of this paper is to demonstrate how technology can push boundaries for making public toilets more inclusive in the urban context, and further identify the challenges and limitations of the same. This is carried out with the development of a theoretical understanding of the dimensions of accessibility in public toilets as well as defining the indicators of accessibility and inclusion in public toilets. The indicators are derived from the existing seven principles of universal design and the five principles of universal design India, in addition to the four 'POUR principles' for accessible technologies defined by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C).

2. Theoretical Understanding

The theoretical framework for this paper begins with defining the dimensions of inclusion in public toilets with respect to technology and innovation. Article 9 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) is about accessibility and defines its purpose as one that ensures access of persons with disabilities on an equal basis with everyone across the aspects of the physical environment, information & communication along with all services and facilities available to the public (UNCRPD, 2007). This definition gives rise to the technological dimensions of infrastructure (physical environment), information and services for inclusion, which shall be the three dimensions discussed in this paper through distinct national and international case examples (Figure 1).

Figure 1. *Three Dimensions of Accessibility in Public Toilets.*

Source: *Authors*

2.1 Accessibility through Information

Information has various forms ranging across digital and physical media including text, audio/video, images, etc. UNESCO (2022) defines information accessibility in terms of the ‘availability, accessibility and affordability of information’. NHS (n.d.) defines accessible information as that ‘which is able to be read or received and understood by the individual or group for which it is intended’. In the context of public toilets, accessibility in information or information accessibility, may be understood via three dimensions – the physical or ‘low-tech’ dimension (which includes signage, notices, etc.) and the ‘high-tech’ or the digital dimension (which includes apps, web-based content, etc.). At the receiving end, it is important to consider the above mentioned three dimensions with respect to the diversity of human needs across age, ability, gender, and socio-economic status.

2.2 Accessibility in Infrastructure

Infrastructure in the context of public toilets refers to the built components including the public toilet structure, cubicles, fixtures, lighting, dispensers etc. The understanding herein lies at how technology intervenes in each of these individual components along with the role it can play in bringing all these components together in a harmonious manner to provide a seamless inclusive experience to users with disabilities and diverse needs. Like the previous section, this aspect also has two dimensions. The first being the low-tech dimension (includes interventions involving minimal automation or use of higher order electronic equipment), for example, building an accessible ramp or changing the built layout of the toilet itself to accommodate persons with disabilities or diverse needs. The second dimension is high-tech (includes integration of higher-order electronic technologies), for example, sensor-based technologies in public toilets.

2.3 Accessibility through Services

Services is a multi-dimensional aspect which covers dimensions of maintenance and management, to provide improved public toilet experiences to all. Using modern technologies and innovation, it is possible to create and develop unique and effective service models of public toilets that cater to enhance the experience of users with diverse needs while also promoting other aspects like the economic and / or the environmental dimensions, thus addressing the three distinct dimensions of sustainability with a single model. In the case of public toilets, this involves the understanding the role of various stakeholders including primary, secondary, and tertiary, as they would all contribute at different phases of the model in different capacities.

2.4 Indicators of an Accessible Technology or Implementation

An accessible technology (or implementation of various technologies) would have various ways in which it is accessible and identifying the same needs defining certain indicators. For this paper, the seven principles of universal design (Connell et al., 1997), five universal design India principles (Khare et al., 2012) and the four POUR principles given by the W3C for accessible ICTs (World Wide Web Consortium, 2016) serve as the foundation for defining the indicators. Combining and considering the overlaps between the three sets of principles, the indicators are formulated as follows:

- A. **Perceivable:** This indicator combines ‘Perceptible Information’ from the seven principles of universal design and P for ‘Perceivable’ from the POUR principles for ICTs. It indicates that the technology should be able to effectively communicate relevant information regarding its use, regardless of any ambient disturbances or diverse needs of the user.
- B. **Equitable:** This indicator is common between two sets as ‘Equitable Use’ from the seven principles of universal design and ‘Equitable’ from the five universal design India principles. It indicates that the technology does not discriminate and is fair to all users with diverse needs.
- C. **Operable & Flexible:** This indicator combines ‘Flexibility in Use’ from the seven principles of universal design, ‘Usable’ from the five universal design India principles and O for ‘Operable’ from the POUR principles for ICTs. It indicates that the technology is effectively and efficiently operable by maximum number of different users and is accommodative of different preferences and abilities.

- D. Simple to Understand & Use: This indicator combines ‘Simple and Intuitive Use’ from the seven principles of universal design and U for ‘Understandable’ from the POUR principles for ICTs. It indicates that the technology is easy to comprehend and use effectively, regardless of the prior level of education, knowledge, language, experience in a particular domain, or skills of the user.
- E. Tolerance for Error: This indicator combines ‘Tolerance for Error’ from the seven principles of universal design and R for ‘Robust’ from the POUR principles for ICTs. It indicates that the technology is designed and implemented with sufficient alternative options for performing its function and minimising negative consequences in the case the technology, or a part of it, fails.
- F. Optimised Physical or Tangible Features: This indicator is derived from ‘Size and Space for Approach and Use’ from the seven principles of universal design. If the technology has a physical or a tangible form, features, or activity in its usage, it needs to be ensured that these features are optimised appropriately for use by maximum number of people with diverse needs.
- G. Culturally Appropriate: This indicator is derived from ‘Cultural’ principle from the five universal design India principles. It indicates that the technology should fit the varied cultures and associated preferences of all the communities that would be interacting with it.
- H. Affordable: This indicator is derived from ‘Economy’ principle from the five universal design India principles. It indicates that the technology is economically feasible and usable by people from all economic backgrounds.
- I. Aesthetics: This indicator is derived from ‘Aesthetic’ principle from the five universal design India principles.

It indicates that the ‘look’ and ‘feel’ of the technology is appealing to all users, while its various elements like form, colour, texture, etc. also play a role in informing the user of its usability, safety, and other dimensions.

3. Case Studies

3.1 Information and Communication-Based Examples

As discussed previously (see section 2.1), accessibility through information has two dimensions of physical or low-tech and digital or high-tech. Case examples demonstrating inclusion in the context of public toilets through low-tech measures (like signage / symbol design) and high-tech digital measures (like accessible toilet maps) are discussed as follows:

3.1.1 Gender-Neutral Toilet Signage: Cases from USA and India

Signage is an example of the physical or low-tech dimension of information, and in the context of public toilets, appropriate gender-neutral or gender-inclusive signage / icon is of significant discourse and relevance. Well-meaning efforts are being taken and here two such attempts at designing a gender-neutral signage are discussed.

San Francisco International Airport brought in Gensler in 2016 to design a symbol for their new ‘all-gender restrooms’ (Ross, 2018). The context being an international airport brought in numerous challenges including high legibility (quick readability and from various heights and distances) and understandability of the symbol by all user groups (without text-based support regardless of their language backgrounds). The team collected all precedent logos and icons and conducted focus group discussions of groups having diverse gender

representations. The insights highlighted the primary need of safety – the sign should not ‘single them out’ or ‘identify them as a target’, along with the need to be ‘equal’ when compared to the nearby men’s and women’s symbols. The results of the study showed that majority of the users prefer the symbol / icon to portray only the fixtures inside the restroom rather than the gender markers (Figures 2 and 3). Similar efforts are being taken in India. Lopez Design developed a gender-neutral icon for the public toilets and wayfinding signs in the newly developed Kartavya Path (earlier Rajpath) in New Delhi (Lopez Design, 2022). The signs incorporated bilingual text with a non-binary symbol, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 2. Participants reaction highlighting preference of neutral symbols.

Source: Gensler

Figure 3. Final Design proposed by Gensler.

Source: Gensler

Figure 4. Gender Neutral Symbol designed for the newly developed Kartavya Path in New Delhi by Lopez Design.

Source: Lopez Design

3.1.2 Accessible Toilet Maps: Case from United Kingdom (UK)

In an urban context, location of the toilet and information about the accessibility of the toilet are critical pieces that if digitally curated to develop ‘accessible toilet maps’ for informing citizens. The Great British Public Toilet Map (TGBPTM) is an example of the same. Based on a crowdsourcing model, the map is an open dataset of publicly accessible toilets which allows people to locate toilets through an online interface along with the option of adding, editing, or removing data. Earlier, datasets created only by online mining, open-data or crowdsourcing proved ineffective and hence, a new methodology was developed that combined the strengths of all methods to create dataset that updates based on inputs from both the providers as well as the users (Ramster & Bichard, 2014). Figure 5 shows a typical interface of TGBPTM, with the locations marked on a visual map along with options of filtering, adding a toilet and finding a toilet. Figure 6 highlights the available information of directions, available accessibility features, fee and opening hours. It is to be noted that the correctness of the information is also asked from every user along with basic information about when was the last time the information was updated.

Figure 5. Interface of The Great British Public Toilet Map (TGBPTM).

Source: <https://www.toiletmap.org.uk/>

Figure 6. Screen showing information after selecting a location in TGBPTM.

Source: <https://www.toiletmap.org.uk/>

3.2 Infrastructure-Based Examples

As discussed previously (see section 2.2), accessibility in infrastructure has two dimensions of low-tech and high-tech. Case examples demonstrating inclusion in the context of public toilets through low-tech measures and high-tech measures are discussed as follows:

3.2.1 Child-Friendly Toilets: Case from Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu, India

In Tiruchirappalli, children from the urban slums used to defecate in the open drains, and this led Mr. S. Damodaran, the founder of an NGO named 'Gramalaya', to design and implement children-friendly toilets, an initiative which began in the year 2000. The program kept on improvising and the outcomes were examples of low-tech infrastructure-based solutions for inclusive public sanitation practices.

The design considers the provision of handwash and cleaning facilities that are accommodative of the person accompanying the child. It is a flexible design that is customisable as per the space available. The design was built as an extension, or a component of the community toilet itself. At first, septic tanks were used for the community toilets. Later, they were connected to a biogas plant so that cooking gas could be produced. For this, the sludge was mixed with vegetable and food waste produced by slum dwellers and surrounding marketplaces. Fifteen gas stoves in the community kitchen were linked to the gas that was thus produced. An incinerator was added as well to the community toilets to dispose soiled sanitary napkins (NIUA, 2018).

The maintenance model of the larger community toilet involves women self-help groups (SHG) along with a pay and use system using a daily token or a monthly pass. However, there is no user fee for children, elderly, and persons with disabilities in these toilets. The children friendly toilet, as shown in Figure 7, showcases a design that is easy and safe for children to use. One can also observe the smaller toilet seat design suited for children along with attractive and colourful visuals in the wall to promote use by children and impart a pleasant experience. This initiative played a significant role

in making Tiruchirappalli as the first Indian city with slum practices that were open defecation free (NIUA, 2018).

Figure 7. Child-friendly toilet design by 'Gramalaya' in Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu.

Source: IHUWASH, NIUA

3.2.2 SHE Toilet: Case from Warangal, Telangana, India

As per studies conducted in Warangal by the Administrative Staff College of India (ASCI), public toilets were in poor and filthy state, which has been ascribed to poor upkeep, a lack of consistent supply of toilet construction and design that lacks scientific rigour. Additionally, there were no facilities in the toilets for children or persons with disabilities. The lack of proper waste disposal for both solid and liquid waste, the absence of separate blocks for men and women having distinct entrances, and safety-related issues due to a lack of privacy all served to discourage users and hinder inclusion. Through these studies, certain key insights were also derived which highlighted safety and privacy as being reasons for avoiding public toilets in the case of women. Based on focus group discussions, it was understood that common entrances for men and women led to men crowding around the toilet blocks which made women feel reluctant to use the public toilets (NIUA, 2018).

To tackle this challenge, the Greater Warangal Municipal Corporation (GWMC) along with other stakeholders,

developed the ‘SHE’ toilets, designed exclusively for women. These public toilets exemplify inclusion through a combination of low-tech and high-tech measures. Key considerations when designing the toilet included a user-friendly entry (with an emphasis on privacy and security), aesthetics, and cleanliness. It was built with standard materials (brick, cement, steel, and prefab fibre cement sheets). One unit typically requires three months to install. These toilets currently only have two seats. They can, however, be expanded to four or more toilet seats. Safety grills have been incorporated to prevent vandalism. In addition to these, other technologies like CCTV, pay and use sanitary pad vending machines, incinerators and customer feedback machines have also been installed in these toilets which enhance the user experience (NIUA, 2018). The toilet being exclusively for women, enhances inclusion for women in the public toilet experience of the larger urban context.

Figure 8. (Left) SHE Toilet for women in Warangal, Telangana. (Right) Woman caretaker inside the toilet with a customer feedback machine.

Source: IHUWASH, NIUA

3.2.3 Smart Toilets: Cases from Japan and India

Full technology-integrated smart or high-tech public toilets are the path towards the future, and they are becoming increasingly popular around the globe. Innovative efforts have been demonstrated, for example, the Tokyo Toilet project by the Nippon Foundation in Japan, which aimed at recreating seventeen public toilets ‘as a step towards a society that embraces diversity’ by making them more accessible regardless of gender, age, and ability (The Nippon Foundation, 2022). The toilets are in Shibuya, Tokyo, all designed by renowned architects and designers.

The design of these the Tokyo Toilets highlights the potential of modern technologies for enabling inclusion and accessibility in public toilets. An example would be the hemispherical Hi Toilet, as shown in Figure 9. Designed by Kazoo Sato, the public toilet uses voice command features to control various functions including the doors, the taps, the toilet flush as well as the ambient music. There are audio-based systems installed in the toilet with automated voice messages which explain the users as they enter about using the voice command features. For preventing odour, a 24-hour ventilation system has been put in place (Griffiths, 2022). The voice and audio assistance technology, in addition to other infrastructural components as shown in Figure 10, makes the toilet more accessible for persons with disabilities, apart from other existing accessibility features.

Figure 9. *Hi-Toilet in Tokyo, Japan, designed by Kazoo Sato.*

Source: *Dezeen*

Figure 10. *Hi-Toilet in Tokyo, Japan, designed by Kazoo Sato.*

Source: *Dezeen*

Indian government agencies, under the Smart Cities Mission, has been undertaking projects of developing smart public toilets across various cities. For example, the Ahmedabad Municipal Corporation (AMC) has built smart public toilets in the city as shown in Figure 11. The toilets are pay and use and only open if a coin is inserted in the slots as shown in figure 12. There is CCTV integration for safety, automatic lighting, auto-flushing mechanisms along with auto-cleaning

technology as soon as the user exits the toilet (Smart Cities Council, 2020).

Figure 11. Smart Toilet in Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

Source: PNI

Figure 12. Paid entry to smart toilet with information in local language in Ahmedabad, Gujarat.

Source: Authors

3.3 Services-Based Examples

Services, as mentioned earlier, include aspects of maintenance and management, which are critical for the overall experience of any user in a public toilet. Innovation and technological interventions can make the process of maintaining and managing public toilets in an urban context efficient. Here, two such ways are discussed – one of monitoring public toilets using Internet of Things (IoT) based means and the other showcases innovative and novel service models of developing public toilets like ‘mobile toilets’.

3.3.1 Public Toilet Monitoring Systems

Partnering with various private companies, the government and municipal corporations are integrating IoT based real-time public toilet monitoring systems which ensures cleanliness of toilets and brings more accountability to the vendors, for example, Municipal Corporation of Gurugram (MCG) partnered with a private firm to launch public toilet monitoring systems with 126 public toilets geo-tagged and under monitoring (Regelman, 2022). Most of these technologies involve a one-point dashboard that lets the authorities monitor the status and take necessary actions effectively and timely. Numerous studies have highlighted the potential of IoT based monitoring systems for public toilets. Deshmukh et al. (2020) in their study have shown the ability to measure various parameters in a public toilet using IoT and machine learning. The parameters include which includes odour, PPM levels, water level, cleaner’s attendance using RFID tags, etc. A dashboard (Figure 14) to be viewed on the cleaner’s phone is also proposed, thus preventing him to visit each toilet under his supervision, just to find out the status of cleanliness and odour. Since cleanliness and hygiene have been identified as reasons of avoiding using public toilets in

the Indian urban context (Purkayastha and Raheja, 2022), the monitoring systems discussed above can aid to make public toilets more accessible in this regard.

Figure 12. Dashboard in cleaner's mobile app generated using the public toilet monitoring system.

Source: (Deshmukh et al., 2020)

3.3.2 Innovative Public Toilet Service Models

There are various innovative models being developed by various entrepreneurial ventures as well as government bodies for public toilets which enhances serviceability. An example of this is the model of converting old buses into toilets and placing them at locations with high demand. This idea has been implemented in multiple places, including Pune and Bengaluru where the attempts are focused on making such toilets only for women. In Pune, this initiative was named as 'Ti Toilet' project and was undertaken by an entrepreneurial venture while in Bengaluru, these toilets are known as

‘Sthree’ toilets and the initiative is being carried out by the Karnataka State Road Transport Corporation (KSRTC). Both models have several commonalities as the ‘Sthree’ toilet model was developed taking inspiration from the ‘Ti Toilet’ model including the availability of necessary amenities like sanitary pads, breastfeeding chair, etc. (The Economic Times, 2020). Integration of features like panic buttons and diaper-changing stations, especially in the ‘Sthree’ toilets, have made these toilets more inclusive. (Philip, 2020) The service model benefits the entire chain as it provides use to old and dysfunctional buses, while it caters to placing new public toilets at strategic locations like crowded bus stands, without building an entirely new one.

Figure 13. 'Ti Toilet' in Pune, Maharashtra, converted from an old bus.

Source: NDTV

Figure 14. Interior view of 'Sthree' toilet in Bengaluru, Karnataka.

Source: Deccan Herald

Another example of an innovative service model for public toilets is the 'Loo Café', an entrepreneurial initiative which began in Hyderabad and is now scaling to multiple cities across India. The intent of this initiative is to challenge the poor public perception of public toilets, which is also a critical factor that prevents use of public toilets to their full potential. To do so a model was developed and implemented in Hyderabad (Figure 16)- marketed as a 'luxury public washroom'. The facility has free toilets for men, women, and

persons with disabilities, along with other amenities attached like a café that generates revenue and provides a resting space and an ATM. The items served in the café are all priced below 30 INR. A garbage bin and a sanitary napkin vending machine are available in the women's section. Additionally, there is provision of solar panels, security cameras, and air conditioners. An attendant directs infrequent visitors if the need arises, and anyone who might need to use the facilities frequently is issued a free access card. The surfaces are easy to wash. Stink sensors are installed along with a user feedback system that is linked to both the parent company's offices as well as the Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation (GHMC) (Thatipalli, 2018).

Figure 14. Loo Café in Hyderabad, Telangana.

Source: Deccan Chronicle

4. Discussion

To assess the cases discussed in the previous section in terms of the indicators formulated in section 2.4, a matrix (Table 1) of the case versus the indicators is charted as follows, highlighting which indicators have been attempted to be addressed to some extent in the discussed cases.

S. No.	Case	Perceivable	Equitable	Operable & Flexible	Simple to Understand & Use	Tolerance for Error	Optimised Physical Features	Culturally Appropriate	Affordable	Aesthetics
1	Gender Neutral Symbol : Gensler (USA)	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Grey	Yellow	Grey	Green
2	Gender Neutral Symbol : Lopez Design (India)	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Grey	Green
3	The Great British Public Toilet Map (UK)	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow
4	Children-Friendly Toilets in Tiruchirappalli (India)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
5	SHE Toilets in Warangal (India)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
6	Tokyo Toilets (Japan)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green
7	Smart Public Toilets in Ahmedabad (India)	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
8	Public Toilet Monitoring Systems (India)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Yellow	Yellow
9	'Ti Toilet' and 'Stree Toilet' Models (India)	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Green
10	'Loo Cafe' in Hyderabad (India)	Green	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Yellow	Green	Green

Table 1. Discussed Cases and the Indicators for Accessible Technologies / Implementation (Green – addressed, Yellow – unclear/limited information, Grey – inapplicable for context).

Source: Authors

The assessment in Table 1 is based on the authors' understanding. Due to this study being a desk-based review, it is difficult to comment with absolute certainty on whether an indicator has not been addressed entirely in a case and vice versa. Hence, the yellow boxes signify that there is limited information or lack of clarity as to 'how?' in that regard and there is a need for further assessment. For the 'perceivable' indicator, one can identify that primarily all the discussed cases have addressed or attempted to address this as all of them are able to effectively communicate their use to the user. However, the 'culturally appropriate' indicator is the one with the most 'unclear / limited information' markers (8/10) highlighting the possibility that cultural appropriateness as a factor for accessibility and inclusion in technologies for public toilets needs to be considered with more thought and action. 'Tolerance for Error' is also another indicator with a high number of 'unclear / limited information' markers (7/10) highlighting the possible lack of addressing fallback options in case a technology or a part of it fails in a particular scenario. 'Affordability' is another critical dimension, to be considered whilst adopting high-tech interventions into the Indian context, for example, the 'Hi Toilet' voice-enabled technology from Tokyo Toilet project is highlighted as 'unclear / limited information' signifying that there is a need for more detailed investigations into the cost and maintenance factor, which would affect the economic aspect of the public toilets.

5. Concluding Remarks

As this domain of technologies for accessibility and inclusion in public toilets is rapidly evolving, it is necessary to keep in mind the broad indicators that make a technology accessible. It is even more important to determine the nature of accessibility and inclusion with respect to the context of the technology's

application and its surrounding socio-spatial environment. The limitation here is that this review is desk-based and as was identified in this paper, certain crucial indicators of accessibility including ‘tolerance for error’ and ‘cultural appropriateness’ need to be investigated further in the context of accessible technologies for public toilets through more case examples. In addition to developing a clear insight into each of the indicator and its applicability, the way forward from this paper would include the possibility of developing rating criteria for assessment of technologies for accessibility and inclusion in public toilets. This would in turn aid in contextualising existing technologies for the Indian ground scenario to improve the current state of public toilets in India.

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